
87. Radial velocities: results from DR3

GAIA'S radial velocity spectrometer (RVS) is obtaining spectra of all stars brighter than about $G_{\text{RVS}} \sim 16$ (the magnitude in the spectroscopic bandpass). These will primarily be used to determine the radial velocity of each sufficiently bright star through its measured Doppler shift. But for millions of the brightest stars, the spectra also yield astrophysical information such as interstellar reddening, α -element abundances and rotational velocities, and even individual abundances for elements such as Fe, Ca, Mg, Ti, and Si.

In earlier essays, I have described why these radial velocity measurements were undertaken as part of the Gaia mission (#8), the choice of the wavelength region for the on-board radial velocity spectrometer (#85), and how the spectra are actually acquired (#86).

While Gaia is, today (Aug 2022), 8 years into a possible 10-year mission, results for only the first 34 months of data (Jul 2014–May 2017) have been processed and released by the Gaia Data Processing and Analysis Consortium, as Gaia Data Release 3 on 13 June 2022.

Along with 1.8 billion sources with astrometric data, DR3 provides radial velocities for more than 33 million down to $G_{\text{RVS}} \sim 14$ mag. When DR4 is released in 2025, based on 66 months of data, results for the 100 million sources down to $G_{\text{RVS}} \sim 16$ mag should be available.

ALTHOUGH I WILL NOT detail the complexities of the pipeline processing needed to create these results, it is worth stressing that many effects must be included and carefully calibrated (Katz et al. 2022).

Amongst them are the effects of straylight, calibration of the line-spread function (both along- and across-scan), the effects of CCD bias, saturation, and dark current, the flagging of cosmic rays, the handling of crowded regions and overlapping samples. All this is followed by the detection of emission lines and spectral breaks, eventually leading to the extraction of astrophysical information including the radial velocity and rotational broadening velocity.

But here I will focus exclusively on some of the first scientific results that have accompanied the DR3 radial velocities, recently reported by Katz et al. (2022).

Radial velocity spectrometer results in Data Release 3	
Limiting magnitude of RVS results in DR3	$G_{\text{RVS}} \sim 14$
Temperature interval, $G_{\text{RVS}} < 12$	3100–14 500 K
$G_{\text{RVS}} > 12$	3100–6750 K
Sources with radial velocities	33 812 183
Sources with mean G_{RVS} -band magnitudes	32 232 187
Sources with rotational velocities	3 524 677
Mean RVS spectra	999 645
Variables with radial-velocity time series	1 898
Astrophysical parameters from RVS spectra	5 591 594
Chemical abundances from RVS spectra	2 513 593
Diffuse interstellar band in RVS spectra	472 584

I WILL ILLUSTRATE these remarkable results through just some of the diagrams included in their paper. The first, below, simply shows the sky distribution, in Galactic coordinates (centred on the Galactic centre), of the 33 million stars having a combined radial velocity in GDR3. The sampling of the map is approximately 0.2 square degrees.

THE TOP FIGURE on the next page shows the histogram of the combined radial velocities. The bulk of the sources belong to the Milky Way disk, and are centred around ~ 0 km s^{-1} .

Two specific groups of objects stand out in the right wing of the distribution: the Large Magellanic Cloud appears as a bump around $+262$ km s^{-1} , while the high-velocity globular cluster NGC 3201 is visible as a spike around $+494$ km s^{-1} .

Beneath that, the map of the median radial velocities as a function of Galactic longitude and latitude reveals the rotation of the Galactic disk (projected along the lines-of-sight), manifested by the alternation of bright areas (with positive median velocities) and dark areas (with negative median velocities).

Several objects whose radial velocities differ from those of their close environment (and which are sufficiently populated to affect the median value), are visible by their local contrast. In addition to the Large and Small Magellanic Clouds appearing as bright spots in the lower right region of the sky distribution, the Sagittarius dwarf galaxy is visible as a faint quasi-vertical stripe below the Galactic centre. Several globular clusters and other compact objects appear as small dots in the image, including the globular clusters 47 Tuc and Omega Cen.

THE FIGURE at the top of the next column embraces the distribution of high-velocity stars, those beyond the ± 250 – 500 km s^{-1} wings of the measured radial velocity distribution. Samples are colour-coded, and show all 37.5 million sources successfully processed by the pipeline (red), the 33.8 million sources that passed the validation filters, including a cut at $S/N=2$ (black), the 25.3 million with $S/N \geq 5$ (blue) and the 13.3 million with $S/N \geq 10$ (green).

The flat extended wings of the red curve are likely to be dominated by spurious velocities (stars with velocities above 750 km s^{-1} , notably the hypervelocity stars, being extremely rare in the Galaxy), while the higher S/N cuts remove most of the spurious solutions. Evidence of the higher velocities of the Large Magellanic Cloud stars, and especially the high velocity globular cluster NGC 3201, are clearly seen after applying the filters.

AMONGST PARTICULAR objects discussed by Katz et al., including the open clusters NGC 2516 and Mamacjek 4, and the LMC, I conclude with two figures illustrating the radial velocities in the globular cluster 47 Tuc.

In the colour–magnitude diagram (top) all stars with DR3 photometry are shown as grey dots. Stars with a DR3 radial velocity are colour-coded by their formal uncertainties. In the sky distribution in equatorial coordinates (bottom), stars are colour-coded by their G magnitude. The limit of the spectroscopic processing is visible as a relatively sharp cut around $G \sim 15$ mag.

Radial velocities are measured throughout the cluster, including the densest regions of the core. They cover the upper part of the red giant branch, the asymptotic giant branch, and the horizontal branch. The formal uncertainties improve with magnitude, and are of order a few km s^{-1} at the level of the horizontal branch and of a few hundreds m s^{-1} at the tip of the red giant branch.

LOOKING TO THE 100 million radial velocities expected in DR4, ‘deep learning’ methods are being developed to best identify spurious velocities, minimise the contamination, and maximise the completeness.